
Female Work-life Balance and Employee Engagement in the Nigerian Oil and Gas Sector.

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research is to investigate the relationship between work-life balance and employee engagement of oil and gas companies in south-south, Nigeria. The study used six hundred and twenty-four (624) employees as study population. Two hundred and Forty-four (244) copies of questionnaire were administered to managers and supervisors from the 13 quoted oil and gas servicing companies operating within South-South States of Nigeria (Akwa Ibom, Rivers, Cross Rivers, Bayelsa, Delta and Edo State) and two hundred and twenty-two (222) copies were retrieved. The statistical analysis was conducted using Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study indicate that work-life balance is positively and significantly relate to employee engagement oil and gas companies in south-south, Nigeria. The study recommends that organizations should make deliberate efforts to improve the work-life balance of employees as it will create a sense of belonging and persuade them to believe in and support the company's mission and values.

Keywords: Work-Life Balance, Employee Engagement, family interferes with work (FIW), work interferes with family (WIF), Physical Engagement, Emotional Engagement, Cognitive Engagement.

Introduction

It is particularly critical for organisations to stay up to date with the increasingly difficult problems they encounter in the business sector at this moment, when the majority of firms are slowing down because of the epidemic (Nguyen & Pham, 2020). Organizations need to adapt to the current climate and adopt strategies that set them apart from competitors (Fakhri et al., 2020). One can measure an organization's efficacy by how productive its employees are. You cannot expect to perform at your best without bringing a positive attitude and demeanour to the office. According to Strom et al. (2014), "engaged workers are the lifeblood of successful businesses." Kennedy and Daim (2010) pointed out that research indicates a direct correlation between employee engagement and a company's success. Having engaged employees may help a business in many ways, one of which is lower employee turnover (Haivas et al., 2013), increased organizational citizenship behaviour (Rasheed et al., 2013), and enhanced performance (Buil et al., 2019).

According to Falkoski (2012), disengagement has several detrimental effects such as decreased sales and profitability, disgruntled customers, a less safe workplace, and the departure of valued staff members. Employee engagement, however, has advantages like boosted productivity and less worry. The importance of employee engagement demands that it be the company's top priority. Understanding the factors that most affect employee engagement can help companies increase employee engagement (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The objectives of an organization like oil and gas companies cannot be achieved where employees are dissatisfied and psychologically disengaged from their superiors and organizations (Guion, 2010). Employee engagement tends to result in a readiness to commit to the overall organization. The level of engagement an employee receives can influence the employee's ability to execute the assigned task. Employee engagement has been reported as been vital for enhancing organizational productivity, employee retention, customer satisfaction, achieving competitive advantage and contributing significantly to organizational performance and effectiveness (Brad et al., 2011).

Robertson and Markwick (2009) found that motivated employees are more likely to act as brand ambassadors, perform 20% better than their peers, and remain with the company. They maintained that engagement could boost a company's productivity, agility, and profit margin. Employees that are engaged put their all into their work, which improves their self-efficacy and wellbeing and increases their support for the company. Employee engagement has incalculable benefits for the company, hence it is crucial that organizations create plans and initiatives to guarantee employee engagement, as they are the key to their success (Clement & Eketu, 2019).

Everybody's jobs and their families are the two most important parts of their lives. How to best balance work and family life has been a matter of discussion among academics and the public. As the number of two-parent and single-parent families rises, and as the number of jobs that demand people to be on-call always rises, it is becoming more and more difficult to balance work and family life. Considered as "a degree of involvement or fit among a person's numerous activities in life that is equally satisfying," work-life balance (Sheikh, 2022). When it comes to striking a balance between work and personal life, flexibility in terms of when, where, and how you get things done is crucial (Priyanka & Chand, 2022). An individual's success in both their professional and personal life depends on their ability to strike a healthy balance between the two (Essien & Baridam, 2023; Oludayo et al., 2018).

Work-family issues have varying impacts on people of different sexes, ages, cultural backgrounds, and occupations (Kang & Wang, 2018). A healthy work-life balance offers advantages and disadvantages. Instability between job and family life, for example, can lead

to stress, health issues, and dissatisfaction. But when work and home life are balanced, people will be happier and more successful overall, and they will be more satisfied with their personal and professional efforts. Employees who have a healthy work-life balance are typically hard-working; thus, any business should prioritize it. Workers that are disinterested in their work place more importance on their personal lives. Employees at Nigerian oil and gas businesses have a lot of work to accomplish because of the country's enormous client base. Thus, a lot of people in the employment, particularly women, struggle to manage their personal and professional life.

Neelam and Tanksale (2014) examined women's work-life balance in higher education. The survey, which included one hundred participants, showed that women spend a wide variety of amounts of time on various tasks within their companies. Compared to their male colleagues, married women in their thirties and twenties who have children find it more difficult to balance work and family obligations. They have difficulties since they must take care of their homes and family. While some of them significantly rely on domestic workers, others send their children to creches. Kshirsagar (2018) examined how women in the service sector manage their job and personal lives. Work-life balance had a significant impact on women's well-being in the firms that were the subject of the study, which looked at how it affects women in the banking and teaching industries. This research work differs from previous work because it investigates the correlation between female work-life balance and employee engagement in Nigeria oil and gas sector.

Statement of the Problem

Engagement of employees is a critical success factor, which if neglected becomes detrimental to the organization. Organizations are faced with problems relating to engagement of skilled employees in recent times (Umoh et al., 2014) and such is also observed amongst oil and gas companies. The observed poor engagement can have a detrimental impact on an organization's success because it shows up as absenteeism, cynical conduct, and turnover. Employee engagement is essential for organisations to have personnel who are prepared to operate consistently in the company's best interests. Engagement is important because it affects performance, motivation, absenteeism, and work withdrawal behaviour (Clement & Eketu, 2019). Lack of engagement poses several problems for the firm. Low engagement leads to high turnover of employee which costs the company in terms of resource development and hence reduces the firm's global competitiveness (Nguyen & Pham, 2020).

Historically, women were more likely to be housewives. As a result, few women left the house to go to their jobs. Women were supposed to submit to their fathers' or husbands' riches and power, so only a small portion of them received education; because of the speed at which the economy is developing, some women have expanded their horizons by learning more about contemporary culture. Women who receive education have a greater chance of finding satisfying employment in addition to becoming more independent. Since speed and accuracy are less important in today's knowledge-based economy than strategic thinking, women have been urged to advance to leadership positions in all fields depending on their own skills (Roebuck et al., 2013; Schueller-Weidekamm & Kautzky-Willer, 2012).

Many working women who already must fulfil several responsibilities at home and at work are finding this new trend stressful. Despite the demands of their employment, they must make time for their families a priority. Working women attempt to balance the demands of their personal and professional lives, which puts a burden on many families. Businesses that want to achieve a healthy work-life balance confront obstacles, as do their female employees. Oil and gas employees generally begin their workdays before daybreak and continue working

late into the evening, making this a particularly difficult industry for women to enter. This is particularly difficult for women, who are usually in charge of caring for the house (Talamala, 2023). Kanthisree (2013) observed that the phrase "work-life balance" (WLB) originated in 1986 as a reaction to the increasing worries of both individuals and organizations regarding the potential impact of work on family life and vice versa. This led to the development of the concepts of "family-work conflict" (FWC) and "work-family conflict" (WFC). The latter situation is known as family interferes with work (FIW), whereas the former one is also known as work interferes with family (WIF). The study seeks to examine the correlation of the dimension of family interference with work and the three measures of employee engagement.

Research Questions

The following research questions will guide the study:

- i. What is the relationship between family interference with work and physical engagement of employees in Nigeria oil and gas sector?
- ii. What is the relationship between family interference with work and emotional engagement of employees in Nigeria oil and gas sector?
- iii. What is the relationship between family interference with work and cognitive engagement of employees in Nigeria oil and gas sector?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested:

H₀₁: there is no significant relationship between family interference with work and physical engagement of employees in Nigeria oil and gas sector.

H₀₂: there is no significant relationship between family interference with work and emotional engagement of employees in Nigeria oil and gas sector.

H₀₃: there is no significant relationship between family interference with work and cognitive engagement of employees in Nigeria oil and gas sector.

Literature Review

Work-Life Balance (WLB)

According to Poulouse and Sudarsan (2014), work-life is a broad topic that has been described in a variety of ways by different scholars using different dimensions. Studies about women in a variety of roles are where the field of work-life balance study first began. Kahn et al. (1964) characterized work-family conflict as "a form of inter role conflict in which the role pressures from work and family domains are mutually incompatible in some respect." This is how work-life balance was first referred to. Stated differently, this means that engaging in the family (job) role makes it harder by nature. The degree to which people are equally involved in and satisfied with their roles in work and family is known as work-life balance (Poulouse & Sudarsan, 2014). An individual's ability to manage the time, emotions, and behaviors required by paid employment, personal obligations, and family duties is another definition of work-life balance (Mohamed et al., 2023). Achieving work-life balance (WLB) involves appropriately balancing one's obligations to one's family, friends, and job with those to one's health, happiness, and leisure. Together with working long hours and intensifying, it also includes prioritizing work above family.

Most studies have focused on the existence of work-family balance, or the frequency and extent to which work interferes with family life or family interferes with work. Work-life balance is influenced by role overload, work-to-family conflict, and work-to-work conflict. Role overload, or having too much to accomplish in too little time, causes stress, fatigue, and

a sense of time restrictions. Finding balance between the time and energy spent on work and personal interests preserves a person's general sense of equilibrium and vigour (Katili et al., 2021). This is known as work-life balance.

Rahman (2019) and Mohamed et al. (2023) state that when a person's professional and personal obligations are inherently in harmony with one another, they have attained "work-life balance" (WLB). We will refrain from interfering with this individual's capacity to carry out their responsibilities, both personal and professional. Complementing these two goals increases the likelihood of success. While challenging, some businesses provide programs to enhance employees' work-related well-being. Both the influence of outside events and the individual's participation to the creation of this pleasant situation are equally important. Businesses can boost employee productivity by implementing WLB initiatives. According to Solihu et al. (2023), production tends to rise when WLB goals are met on both an individual and group level.

Sheikh (2022) asserts that workers' output and personal lives are significantly impacted by their capacity to maintain a work-life balance. The work-life balance of employees is one of the elements that can impact their productivity (Mendis & Weerakkody, 2017). Studies have demonstrated that those who can effectively manage their personal and professional spheres have greater levels of fulfillment in both domains. According to Essien and Baridam (2023), striking a balance between job and personal life might be difficult. Fakhri et al. (2020) discovered that the two biggest determinants of an individual's personal life relative to others are role conflict and workload. A negative perspective on one's capacity to achieve a healthy work-life balance was linked to both, it was discovered. According to this, employees who face higher levels of role conflict and hardship may also see a decline in their work-life harmony.

According to Omar et al. (2015), "role conflict" is the term used to characterise the conflict that can arise when a person's commitments to their job and their personal life conflict. Therefore, it seems to reason that stress in one area of life, like one's employment, can make one too worn out, irritable, or preoccupied with work-related matters to properly interact with their loved ones at home (Sheikh, 2022; Solihu et al., 2023).

Employees may grow angry at work, feel exhausted, and think about leaving if a healthy work-life balance is not promoted. These issues can make people more irritable and agitated, which can lower their degree of life satisfaction. In a similar vein, employees who bring problems from home to work risk being distracted and making the already chaotic situation worse (Al-Khateeb & Al-Louzi, 2020). Stress, strained muscles, headaches, weight gain, and depression are all related to work-life balance, and women in the workforce are more likely than males to report these problems (Eniola, 2023). A person's health, happiness, and quality of life may suffer as a result of the stress of attempting to strike a balance between their personal priorities and those of their company (Essien & Baridam, 2023). The working class is increasingly demanding the freedom to establish their own work-life balance in today's fast-paced, individualistic society (Fakhri et al., 2020).

Family interference with work (FIW):

Family interference with work, sometimes referred to as family-work conflict (FWC) or personal life interference with work (PLIW), is the term used to describe family demands that make it more difficult for an individual to fulfil workplace commitments and responsibilities. Conflicts at work occur when personal obligations conflict with those of the workplace. The term "family interference with work" describes the difficulties and disputes that occur when

workers' duties and family responsibilities have an impact on their output, performance, and general well-being at work. This aspect of work-life balance covers a range of challenges that workers have while juggling the demands of their professions with their responsibilities as parents, carers, or other family members (Iqbal et al., 2023).

The degree to which role demands originating from the family domain are incompatible with the job domain is referred to as family interference with work conflict. Stated differently, the virtue of involvement in which the professional role complicates the involvement in the family role (Al-Khateeb & Al-Louzi, 2020). Family issues may have an impact on workplace conflict. Several studies investigating the causes of family interference with work-related conflict have looked at the structural characteristics of the family environment. Some examples of the antecedents include the number and ages of children, whether the spouse or partner works, and the responsibilities of the children, but this list is not exhaustive. Essien and Baridam (2023) found that regardless of the age of the children, men and women with children were more likely than those without children to experience family interference with job conflict. Additionally, Katili et al. (2021) discovered that differences in household chores, financial matters, and leisure activities were important predictors of family interference with work conflict.

Research has shown that individuals with a variety of demands from their family obligations are more likely to have family interference with work-related disputes (Mahajan & Guleria, 2022; Mohamed et al., 2023; Mungania, 2017). Parenting is the family antecedent that most consistently predicts family interference with work (Sheikh, 2022). After analyzing the connection between family interference, employment, and parenting, Parenting modifies men's and women's roles in the home and at work, according to Sheikh (2022) research. Conversion to motherhood is linked to women spending more time in the home domain; this is accomplished by modifying work obligations to meet the needs and activities of the family (Schueller-Weidekamm & Kautzky-Willer, 2012). According to Kshirsagar (2018), men who become fathers tend to prioritize their employment more and work longer hours. Fathers who are new and have not yet made their financial reputation may feel pressured to work.

Studies show that when people become parents, their marital satisfaction declines (Mohamed et al., 2023). The causes for the decrease in marital happiness are an increase in childcare and domestic obligations. These added obligations increase stress, which in turn affects roles at work and at home (Prakash et al., 2016). There is a greater chance of increased conflict between work and family roles throughout the transition to motherhood when one is exposed to more role activities in both work and family domains. According to a study by Feeney and Stritch (2019), having young children in the house is thought to be a major contributing factor to gender inequalities in the work-family interaction. When children needed more money and time resources from their parents, there were greater gender inequalities.

Researchers have looked closely at the roles that job and family play in the lives of those who work. According to Glavin and Schieman (2022), researchers studying work and family dynamics must adopt a new strategy when studying people who play dual roles. Studying role conflict in isolation is no longer the best technique for examining work and family responsibilities; instead, a more constructive integration of a person's self-disrespect throughout their multiple roles is needed. According to Glavin and Schieman (2022), people can maintain a healthy balance between their responsibilities to their families and their jobs by sustaining norms of accountability in each role. Fakhri et al. (2020) concur with Glavin and Schieman (2022) that researchers need to pay more attention to the advantages of balancing work and family responsibilities.

Work interference with family (WIF):

Work-family interference can be defined as a form of inter-role conflict in which the demands of the roles in the work and family domains are incompatible. Other names for it include work-life interference with personal life (WIPL) and work-family conflict (WFC). A common problem in organisations is work interference with family, which happens when an individual's capacity to fulfil commitments and responsibilities to their family is impeded by the demands of their job. If not handled well, this conflict may have detrimental effects on organisations and employees alike. When the family domain is invaded, employees' time, physical resources, and emotional resources are all affected. Interference beyond what an employee can accept or expect can have a severe influence on their sense of job satisfaction, sense of belonging to the organisation, and even their physical and mental health. According to Glavin et al. (2020), work interference with family has been linked to a number of important individual and organisational consequences, according to several researchers. For example, it has been found to negatively link with job attitudes and performance and positively correlate with intends to quit, distress, and burnout. Work interfering with personal lives, such as families and other obligations, can lead to a decrease in employees' job satisfaction. Making employees work on the weekends against their will is one method to reduce job satisfaction and, more significantly, customer satisfaction with the boss. Research on work-family conflict and work/life satisfaction was reviewed by Omar et al. (2015). Overall, work-family conflict and job satisfaction are strongly and negatively correlated across all populations, according to the results.

To meet the expectations of their families, employees may attempt to reduce their work commitment, according to Sheikh (2022). Nonetheless, employees who score well on work-family interference may also be more likely to place a higher value on getting satisfaction from their family, which may result in a decline in task performance (TP) and organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB). Role conflicts and time limits are other factors that may make going above and beyond challenging (Talamala, 2023). The direction of the relationship is uncertain in terms of performance because better corporate citizenship and task completion may also lead to more work-family conflict. Sheikh (2022) found that job interference with family has a negative impact on organisational citizenship behaviour in a sample of teachers, going beyond work satisfaction and organisational commitment. Banahene et al. (2017) found that the individual initiative form of organisational citizenship activity was strongly positively correlated with work interfering with family. However, their conclusions might only be relevant to the corporate citizenship initiative subgroup. Since employees have more control over the more capricious organisational citizenship behaviour, it seems more likely that increasing work interference with family will deprive organisational citizenship behaviour of resources than that increasing organisational citizenship behaviour will inevitably lead to increased work interference with family.

Work Enhancement of Personal Life (WEPL)

The term "work enhancement of personal life," sometimes referred to as "work-life enrichment" or "positive spillover," describes the beneficial impacts that job-related experiences and behaviours can have on a person's relationships, personal growth, and general well-being. Work enhancement highlights the positive aspects of work that lead to personal fulfilment and enrichment, in contrast to work-family conflict, which focusses on the detrimental effects of work on personal life. The ability to integrate abilities learned in the workplace in daily life is provided to individuals (Pradita & Franksiska, 2020). According to Putri et al. (2023), The term "Work Enhancement of Personal Life" (WEPL) describes how much an individual's personal life is improved by their efficiency at work. Increased job satisfaction and less stress at work are associated with higher WEPL scores. WEPL

demonstrated how they are happy with their jobs because their work life replenishes resources that are useful in their personal lives. Employees who believe their work enhances their personal life are more accountable and in charge of their work lives, feel a sense of duty to the organization, and typically stay with the company longer (Sutin et al., 2023). These workers have a great feeling of dedication and loyalty to the business. Workers whose lives have been better because they have more time for friends, family, and leisure also take better care of their health and keep good ties with their coworkers. Their increased productivity at work is another outcome of their effort. Stress and absenteeism are reduced when one's personal life at work is improved. Among the organisational tactics to enhance workers' personal lives are teleworking, flexible scheduling, job redesign, job sharing, and leaves, according to Idris (2014) and Davidescu et al. (2020). Technological advancements have altered when, how, and how we work (Roy, 2016). Technology has made it possible for employees to work after conventional business hours, allowing them to spend more time with friends and family both during and after work hours. Technology advancements have also made communication easier, faster, and more seamless. This has also reduced the gap between workers and their families, particularly when the worker must be at work to finish a task.

Employee Engagement

It is commonly established in organizational literature that employee engagement is a concept (Tiwari & Lenka, 2020). The morale approach study gave rise to this concept in the 1920s. According to Rabuana and Yanuar (2023) and Utami and Sudiro (2023), employee engagement is described as an individual's consent to fulfill job-related responsibilities, encompassing their physical, mental, and emotional welfare while working. According to Rabuana and Yanuar (2023) and Utami and Sudiro (2023), employee engagement is defined as a worker's mental, emotional, and behavioral condition that is focused on company goals and objectives. According to Shah et al. (2018), "engrossing" employees in a way that is real, acceptable, and linked to strategy, development, energy, and enjoyment is the basis of employee engagement as a scientific art form that supports, leverages, and transforms effort into results. It appears that organizations are drawn to the term "employee engagement" in the same proportion as the advisory groups and professional associations that promote it. Employees that are engaged at work are more likely to be profitable, productive, safe, healthy, less likely to quit, and more likely to make discretionary efforts; benefits that most businesses seek, according to research (Othman et al., 2019; Simanjuntak et al., 2023; Utami & Sudiro, 2023; Zanabazar et al., 2023). Moreover, motivated employees have allegedly been shown to generate better revenue and, on average, receive higher customer satisfaction ratings (Anitha, 2014). According to Build et al. (2019), it is not unexpected that corporate executives consistently rank developing a motivated staff as one of their top organizational objectives.

According to Aybas and Acar (2017), employees are deemed "engaged" when they try to give priority to the needs of their organization. Engagement can be impacted by both intrinsic and extrinsic factors, as they include "intense concentration on one's work that ultimately results in the fulfilment of one's most important goals" (Nguyen & Pham, 2020). The degree to which an employee is engaged has a substantial bearing on the challenges that businesses confront in the current economic climate. Many studies have been conducted as a result to determine the precise characteristics of an engaged employee. Someone is considered "engaged" when they give the impression that they are dedicated to their work and their organization. Employee accountability for the organization's performance is higher, and they have a greater emotional stake in its success. Conversely, Rabuana and Yanuar (2023)

defined engagement as the drive to put in the greatest effort and exhibit unity, resolution, and attention throughout the process. It is beneficial for the company when workers who are enthusiastic about what they do produce excellent results. Scholars' ought to investigate significant components that may be applied inherently to boost employee motivation. According to Nguyen and Pham (2020), some of these include having a fulfilling career, feeling emotionally invested in one's work, having a strong work-life balance, intrinsic motivation, transformative leadership, HRM excellence, and having positive perceptions from the organization.

Physical Engagement

This has to do with the amount of mental and physical effort employees put in at work, according to Khan et al. (2019). They found a link between increased self-assurance and the ability to work hard both mentally and physically. The beauty of engagement is in harmony that a person has with his or her role. When one feels completely fulfilled by their profession, participation reaches its peak. Al Ahad and Khan (2020) assert that organizations nowadays prioritize engagement on a universal basis. Engaged employees are the most desirable asset for businesses. It is advantageous to the company as well as its staff. An environment that cares and promotes employee engagement is one that brings out the best in each individual worker. Macey and Schneider (2008) state that most companies use employee engagement surveys to measure employee engagement and determine the elements that affect it. Despite being in use for some time, there is disagreement on the precise meaning of the term "employee engagement" (Thomas, 2009). The terms "job empowerment" and "job involvement" are two instances of this dispute.

Physical work engagement is based on the idea of bodily participation in any kind of activity, according to Khan et al. (2019). Participating in any kind of employment requires people to put in physical effort. People employ their physical power and energy to do tasks. Even if the physical demands of various vocations (such as manufacturing and teaching) can vary, the concept of exerting energy at work remains applicable. For example, an engaged factory worker would be more excited throughout their shift and do the required tasks faster than other staff members. Similarly, a physically engaged teacher would make more library visits, write lectures, and put in more effort throughout the teaching process (which is like performing) to help students understand the content of a lecture (Tiwari & Lenka, 2020).

Energy expenditure during work can be described as the total amount of effort as well as the frequency of effort in terms of physical participation. A football player that is heavily engaged in physical exertion would use more force and run farther to put pressure on opponents and win the ball, according to Al Ahad and Khan (2020); Khan et al. (2019). Therefore, the term "physical work engagement" refers to "the bodily involvement in tasks, objectives, or organizational activities by intentionally and voluntarily utilizing one's energy and effort to execute and complete those objectives, or activities" is suitable in this instance.

Emotional Engagement

Khan et al. (2019) defines emotional labour at work as the process of managing one's emotions during one's job, which serves as the basis for emotional engagement. When working, those who are emotionally committed to their work typically experience joy or pleasant affective states as well as positive feelings about it. Consequently, emotional engagement is defined as the readiness to dedicate oneself to tasks, goals, or organizational actions that are accompanied by positive emotions, such as pride, excitement, or enthusiasm about actively carrying out and accomplishing those tasks, goals, or activities (Aybas & Acar, 2017; Clement & Eketu, 2019).

Khan et al. (2019) suggest that the basis of employees' emotional engagement is their emotional tie with their employer. The secret to creating a happy work environment is to give employees a sense of belonging and to persuade them to believe in and support the company's mission and values. Positive interpersonal relationships, group dynamics, and managerial techniques are some of the strategies Khan listed for making individuals feel secure and reliable. Engaging with people would give them a sense that their job was valuable, that they were safe in their roles, and that their physical and mental aspirations would be encouraged, according to Khan et al. (2019). Furthermore, engagement was described as "the individual's involvement and satisfaction with as well as enthusiasm for work" by Zanabazar et al. (2023). A third way to define emotional engagement is "the degree to which workers dedicate themselves to a project or person within the company, the amount of effort they put in, and the duration of their stay as a result of that dedication." Moreover, he says it's the willingness to invest one's own time and effort to help one's employer succeed.

Emotional engagement, according to Simanjuntak et al. (2023), is the degree to which people find fulfillment in their work and feel appreciated for it. Saks (2006) adopted Kahn's (1990) idea of role-related work engagement, which maintains that a worker is "present" psychologically in a certain role within the company. According to his concept, the work role and the role of an organization member are the two most crucial obligations for most organizational members. Having stated that, he suggested separating organizational engagement from work engagement.

Cognitive Engagement

According to Huang et al. (2022) and Khan et al. (2019), this is dependent on how workers view their work as meaningful, safe (physically, emotionally, and psychologically), and having enough material and intangible resources to do the task needed. According to Huang et al. (2022), another sign of this is the belief held by workers that they get support from superiors, peers, and senior personnel to participate in and/or apply the knowledge and abilities they have gained from training and development options. It is understandable to employees that their employer encourages them to pursue professional growth opportunities. According to Shin and Back (2020), employees' perceptions of formal career management procedures, such as skill-building activities, training programs, and opportunities for personal growth, exist within the organization and influence their prospects of advancing in their field. Li and Lajoie (2022) define cognitive engagement as an evaluation of an employee's understanding and mindset toward their work, the company, the culture, and their level of intellectual commitment to the organization. Shuck and Herd (2012) state that cognitive engagement is the most powerful level of engagement, occurring on a silent, intimate level even though it is not yet behaviorally obvious. Generally, it is possible to quantify cognitive engagement.

Theoretical Framework

Spillover Theory

The theory of spillover suggests that the work and family microsystems may have a beneficial or negative influence on each other. Studies show that rigid temporal and spatial frameworks that control work-family connections usually have negative knock-on effects on time, energy, and behaviour. By enabling people to integrate and overlap work and family responsibilities in terms of time and location, a healthy work-family balance can be attained. There is research to support this. Additionally, there are beneficial spillover benefits linked to job flexibility (Hill et al., 2003). According to the Work-Life Spillover Theory, your environment can have both positive and negative impacts. The following is a summary of this

hypothesis: Your workplace is impacted by your personal life, and vice versa. Both have an impact on your health.

According to Bello and Tanko (2020), According to the fundamental idea of spillover theory, roles are viewed differently when they appear identical. The idea is that the spillover effect, which can be either vertical or horizontal, is a problem with finding a balance between work and family. Both good and bad spillover can happen: an unpleasant experience at work can lead to a negative experience at home, and vice versa. It happens when a person feels fulfilled in one area after being satisfied with an accomplishment in another, and vice versa. A person's job as a family member may influence their actions, emotions, and skills that they can use in their work role and vice versa. The application of this theory makes sense due to its particular focus on the interaction between work and family and its significance for work-life balance research. Spillover theory explains the necessary conditions for maintaining a balance between one's personal and professional lives. A person's personal life may suffer if they bring their work-related unhappiness or mental illness home along with them. Likewise, an individual's career may suffer because of domestic problems like domestic discord. In addition, the spillover theory states that happiness, stability, and contentment in all spheres of a person's life private, professional, and social are necessary for a balanced existence. Spillover theory is based on both positive and negative assumptions. There were negative presumptions that if someone couldn't accomplish their duty commitments in one aspect of their lives, they couldn't do other role chores. The spillover theory's balanced positive premise, on the other hand, maintains that if a person fulfils their role responsibilities with satisfaction, they can carry out their other role responsibilities more successfully. Spillover theory explains how a person's roles in their social, professional, and personal life are inversely related. This implies that positive roles impact other roles negatively as well. It might resemble the day-to-day life of a student or family member. If a student is having a bad day at college or university, for instance, their behaviour at home may shift. According to the family, a relative's mood can be used to assess whether they have had a positive day at university. The theory concludes by stating that an individual can't achieve success in more than one aspect of their life, and this will affect every other part of their life (Khalid, 2023).

Methodology

The target population for this study is the managers and supervisors of quoted oil and gas servicing companies operational within South-South, Nigeria. An accessible population of 624 managers and supervisors from the 13 quoted oil and gas servicing companies operating within South-South States of Nigeria (Akwa Ibom, Rivers, Cross Rivers, Bayelsa, Delta and Edo State) was derived for this study. The sample size of 244 for this study was determined using the Taro Yamane sampling formula (Baridam, 2001). The Bowley's formula offers a proportionate distribution of the total sample size across all 13 quoted oil and gas servicing companies with operational base in South-south, Nigeria. A total of 244 structured questionnaires were distributed but 222 were retrieved and used for the data analysis. A non-parametric test called the Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient was used for the bivariate analysis to look at the correlation between the independent variable and the dependent variable's measures.

Testing of Hypotheses

Table 1: Relationship between Family interference with work (FIW) and measures of employee engagement

		FIW	Physical	Emotional	Cognitive
FIW	Correlation	1.000	-.063	-.090	-.151
	Coefficient				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.349	.182	.025
Physical	N	222	222	222	222
	Correlation	-.063	1.000	-.058	-.145
	Coefficient				
Spearman's rho	Sig. (2-tailed)	.349	.	.388	.030
	N	222	222	222	222
	Correlation	-.090	-.058	1.000	-.178
Emotional	Coefficient				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.182	.388	.	.008
	N	222	222	222	222
Cognitive	Correlation	-.151	-.145	-.178	1.000
	Coefficient				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.025	.030	.008	.
	N	222	222	222	222

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The relationship between the variables – family interference with work and the measures of employee engagement (physical, emotional, and cognitive engagement), are revealed to be significant. The results show that family interference with work significantly contributes and enhances outcomes related to employee engagement such as physical engagement (with $\rho = 0.349$ and $P = 0.01$), emotional engagement (with $\rho = 0.182$ and $P = 0.01$), and cognitive engagement (with $\rho = 0.025$ and $P = 0.01$).

Discussion of findings

Work-Life Balance and Employee Engagement

Work-life balance according to Hutomo and Mujannah (2023) is a balance between an individual's time spent at work and the time spent with friends and family. Clement and Eketu (2019) states that juggling work and family obligations is the main emphasis of work-life balance. Mohanty and Kulkarni (2023) defined work-life balance as "a shortage of conflict or interference between employee and family/life roles." Engagement has a major impact on consumer loyalty, labour productivity, employee retention, and profitability, according to Katili et al. (2021). There is a case to be made for companies that support work-life balance to see improvements in productivity and staff engagement. Al Ahad and Khan (2020) find that businesses that put their employees' needs first can develop and execute work-life balance policies and procedures that encourage employee engagement. A friendly work-life policy and perceived flexibility can boost employee engagement, according to Hutomo and Mujannah (2023). This position aligns with the findings of this study.

Nguyen and Pham (2020) also draw the conclusion that employee engagement is enhanced by recuperation, which is viewed as a component of work-life balance. According to Nguyen and Pham (2020), recuperated workers are more dedicated to and fully focused on their work. On the other hand, employee engagement levels suffer when workers answer phones and emails after hours and on the weekends, leading to friction between their homes and their

jobs, according to Othman et al. (2019). Tension between an employee's family and their wellness is found to be detrimental to the organization by Shah et al. (2018). Job progress and work-life balance have been demonstrated to favourably correlate (Rabuana & Yanuar, 2023). Also, Nguyen and Pham (2020) show that job crafting has a favorable effect on employee engagement, which raises individual employee performance.

Conclusion

The relationship between work-life balance (Family interference with work) and employee engagement is revealed to be positive and significant. The findings of this study demonstrate the role of work-life balance as critical for the organization's level of physical, emotional, and cognitive engagement. In line with the results, the study concludes as follows:

- i. Family interference with work which is the difficulties and disputes that occur when workers' duties and family responsibilities have an impact on their output, performance, and general well-being at work is essential for employee engagement such as physical, emotional, and cognitive engagement of female employees in oil and gas as it significantly emphasizes the employee ability to manage family interference with their job.
- ii. Family interference with work which ensures workers effectively manage household chores, financial matters, and leisure activities from interfering with their job contributes toward improved employee engagement such as physical, emotional, and cognitive engagement of female employees in oil and gas because the employees make deliberate effort to balance family and work demands.
- iii. Family interference with work which ensures employees with a variety of demands from their family obligations create a balance with work obligations advances the required level of responsiveness necessary for employee engagement such as physical, emotional, and cognitive engagement of female employees in oil and gas.

Recommendations

The relationship between work-life balance (Family interference with work) and employee engagement is established herein as significant and positive in the sense that actions or expressions of work-life balance (Family interference with work) can be considered as positively impacting and facilitating employee engagement such as physical, emotional, and cognitive engagement. Furthermore, it is observed that a supportive climate amplifies the features of work-life balance in a manner that enhances its impact on female employee engagement. Thus, in line with the findings of this study, the following recommendations are put forward:

- i. Organizations should ensure that prospective and existing employees possess the right work-life balance. Through a balanced work-life, employees will be bodily involvement in tasks, objectives, or organizational activities by intentionally and voluntarily utilizing their energy and effort to execute and complete activities in record time.
- ii. Organizations should make deliberate effort to improve the work-life balance of employees as it will create a sense of belonging and persuade them to believe in and support the company's mission and values.
- iii. Organizations should ensure workers get support from superiors, peers, and senior personnel to participate in and apply the knowledge and abilities they have gained from training and development options. This will cause them to give priority to the needs of the organization.

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